

New Organotin Compounds with Potential Pesticidal Properties

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A series of organotin compounds were synthesized from substituted anilines through their mercuration with mercuric acetate and subsequent conversion into monochlorotin aniline by refluxing with anhydrous stannous chloride in xylene. The properties of synthesized compounds were studied, and their antifungal and antibacterial characters were evaluated. Some of these compounds were found to possess marked antifungal and antibacterial properties and have therefore shown potential for being used as such in crop protection.

ALTHOUGH aliphatic and aromatic organo-mercury compounds have exhibited potent and effective antifungal and antibacterial activity (Mildner *et al.*¹, Guha-Sircar and Coworkers^{2,8}), the utility of organotin compounds, as fungicides, was first reported by Vanderkerk and Luijten^{4,5}. These compounds have since been used in industry, wood preservation, as biostats in hospital maintenance and in the field of agriculture. Earlier studies on organotin compound were mostly employed on aliphatic groups but very few aromatic ones were so used. Detailed studies on new aromatic organotin compounds were therefore undertaken and series of such compounds from various sources prepared. Simultaneously tests of their fungitoxic and bacteritoxic properties were made to study their utility as fungicides or bactericides.

Experimental

Organotin compounds of aniline and its derivatives were prepared through the twin steps of (i) conversion of aniline or its derivatives into its mercurated compounds as previously reported by Vishnoi⁶ by adopting the method of Dimroth⁷ and subsequently (ii) by conversion of mercurated anilines into their corresponding tin compounds through the use of anhydrous stannous chloride. The position and relative orientation of the acetoxymercury group, in the substituted anilines, as also its conversion into corresponding organotin compounds are shown below.

(The addition of -HgOOCCH_3 and -SnCl group depends upon the nature of substituted anilines).

Mercuration was effected through equimolar quantities of aniline, or its derivatives, and mercuric

acetate in the presence of glacial acetic acid, except in the case of diacetoxy mercury compound, where a ratio of 3:1 molar quantities was employed. The resultant crystalline compounds were recrystallised from acetic acid. The separated compound comprised of the para isomer, the ortho remaining in solution. However, in cases where the para position was already occupied, mercuration was effected at the ortho position. The position of acetoxymercury group in these compounds was ascertained by demercuration, subsequent bromination and identification of the bromo derivatives⁸. Kharasch and Jacobson⁹ had explained the mechanism of mercuration of aromatic amines and established that the mercuration takes place at ortho or para position through an intermediate inorganic mercury compound attached to the amine. The composition of the compound was established through estimation of mercury by the method proposed by Lomholt and Christiansen¹⁰, in which mercury was estimated as mercuric sulphide.

The acetoxymercury aniline or its derivatives were subsequently converted into monochlorotin aniline by refluxing equimolar quantities of acetoxymercury aniline and anhydrous stannous chloride in presence of dried xylene. Xylene was distilled under reduced pressure and the residue was recrystallised from ethanol, benzene or acetone in freezing bath. The yield of the final tin compound varied from 40-55 percent of the theoretical. The composition of tin was established through the

estimation of tin as stannic sulphide. Chlorine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's¹¹ method.

The tin compounds prepared from related acetoxy-mercury aniline together with their properties are tested

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TABLE 1—NATURE AND PROPERTIES OF ORGANOTIN COMPOUNDS FROM SUBSTITUTED ANILINES.

Sl. No.	Starting acetoxymercury compounds with its M. P. °C	Corresponding tin compounds with its M.P. °C	Colour	Properties of tin compounds							Pesticidal activity	
				Composition percent Found		Theoretical		Fungicidal			EC	SA
				Sn	Cl	Sn	Cl	AN	CG	RS		
1.	4-R-aniline (167)	4-R'-(185)	G	47.7	14.0	48.0	14.4	+	+	-	-	-
2.	4-R-6-methylaniline (149)	4-R'-(193)	D.B	45.0	13.1	45.4	13.6	-	-	-	-	+
3.	2:4-di-R-5 methylaniline	2:4di-R'-(170)	Y	56.8	16.8	57.2	17.2	++	+	+	+	+
4.	4-R-6-methoxy aniline (167)	4-R'-(182)	C.B.	42.3	12.5	42.9	12.9	-	+	-	-	-
5.	4-R-5-methoxy aniline (144)	4-R'-(175)	Y.B	42.7	13.0	42.9	12.9	+	+	-	+	+
6.	2-R-4-ethoxyaniline (184)	2-R'-(180)	B.O.	40.3	12.0	40.7	12.6	++	+	-	-	-
7.	4-R-6-chloroaniline (130)	4-R'-(197)	Y	41.7	25.0	42.1	25.3	-	-	-	+	+
8.	4-R-5-chloroaniline (160)	4-R'-(191)	Y	41.6	25.1	42.1	25.3	+	+	+	+	+
9.	4-R-6-nitroaniline (300)	4-R'-(163)	D.Y.O	40.8	12.0	40.6	12.2	+	++	+	+	+
10.	4-R-5-nitroaniline (154)	4-R'-(170)	D.B.	40.4	11.8	40.6	12.2	-	-	-	+	+
11.	2-R-4-nitroaniline (300)	4-R'-(165)	D.R.	40.2	11.6	40.6	12.2	+	-	+	+	++
12.	4-R-3-Chloro-6-methylaniline (230)	4-R'-(165)	D.O.	39.8	24.3	40.1	24.1	++	++	+	+	+
13.	2-R-4-chloro-6-methylaniline (205)	4-R'-(158)	L.O.	40.5	23.8	40.1	24.1	++	++	+	+	+
14.	2-R-4-methyl-6-nitroaniline (195)	2-R'-(167)	Y	38.3	11.2	38.7	11.6	++	++	-	-	-
15.	4-R-3-nitro-6-methylaniline (213)	4-R'-(156)	S.B.	38.4	11.2	38.7	11.1	++	+	-	-	-
16.	4-R-3-chloro-6-methoxyaniline (210)	4-R'-(150)	D.Y.R	37.7	22.7	38.0	22.9	-	-	+	+	+
17.	4-R-3-nitro-6-methoxyaniline (111)	4-R'-(174)	D.C.B	36.4	10.7	36.8	11.0	+	-	-	-	-
18.	2-R-4-nitro-6-methoxyaniline (260)	4-R'-(160)	D.Y.	36.5	10.6	36.8	11.0	-	-	+	-	-

R = acetoxymercury, R' = monochlorotin, G = Grey, D = Dark, B = Brown, R = Red, Y = Yellow, L = Light, C = Chocolate, S = Saffron, O = Orange.

in Table 1. Their structure was established as one earlier attained by acetoxymercury compound in which the acetoxymercury group has been quantitatively replaced by SnCl group (Dimroth⁷; Shishido *et al*¹²), a fact duly corroborated by the absence of any mercury in the final product. This was further confirmed from the I. R. Spectra of these compounds in which peaks of C-Sn bond were prominently exhibited. In addition the migration of mercury was established through quantitative recovery of metallic mercury in the flask after completion of stannation reaction. Further, the substitution by-Sn Cl group could only be effected at ortho and para positions previously occupied by acetoxymercury group.

Pesticidal Properties of synthesized compounds :

Pesticidal properties of prepared compounds were tested for their antifungal characters against three important fungi, namely *Aspergillus niger* (A.N.), *Chaetomium globosum* (C.G.) and *Rhizoctonia solani* (R.S.) and for their antibacterial properties against two bacteria namely, *Escherichia coli* (E.C.) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (S.A.). Zinc-ethylenebisdithiocarbamate (Zineb) was used as the standard. The two properties were tested simultaneously adopting modified paper disc bio-assay method of Loo *et al*¹³. Potato dextrose agar media (Riker and Riker¹⁴) for fungicidal character and Agar-solidified nutrient broth media (MaxLevine¹⁵) for antibacterial characters were adopted for these tests.

The zone of inhibition formed by a concentration of 1×10^{-5} mole/ml of each compound was measured and their relative toxicity in comparison to Zineb worked out, assuming the zone formed by the latter as 100. The pesticidal properties of individual compounds has been shown in terms of increased activity to the extent of 50 (+) and 51-100 per cent (++) and decreased activity as (-) against each in the Table.

Results and Discussions

The results of the bioassay testing have shown that the first three positions for antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* were occupied by monochlorotin aniline compounds containing 4-Cl-6-CH₃, 4-CH₃-6-NO₂ and 3-Cl-6-CH₃ substituents (compounds No. 13, 14 and 12). Single substituents namely, those containing 5-NO₂, 6-CH₃ and 6-OCH₃ groups (Nos. 10, 2 and 4) showed relative lesser activity.

The activity against *Chaetomium globosum* was best exhibited by 3-Cl-6-CH₃, 4-CH₃-6-NO₂ and 4-Cl-6-CH₃ analogues of monochlorotin aniline (compounds No. 12, 14 and 13). But in descending order the other substituents containing 4-NO₂, 6-Cl and 3-NO₂-6-OCH₃ groups (Nos. 11, 7 and 17) have shown slightly decreased activity. *Rhizoctonia solani*: Showed greatest inhibition by 4-NO₂, 6-NO₂ and 5-Cl substituents (Nos. 11, 9 and 8) but diminished activity from analogues containing 5-NO₂ and 5 and 6-OCH₃ groups (Nos. 10, 5 and 4).

The bactericidal properties of these compounds as compared to Zineb, were best exhibited by 4-NO₂, 4-Cl-6-CH₃ and 5-NO₂ analogues of monochlorotin aniline (compound Nos. 11, 13 and 10) against both *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The compounds including 4-monochlorotin aniline (No. 1) and its 4-NO₂-6-OCH₃ and 6-CH₃ analogues (Nos. 18 and 2) exhibited diminished activity against both bacteria.

In summary it would be evident that the tin compounds described in the present paper are potentially very effective fungicide or bactericide and in many cases the two characters have been combined in the same compounds. These compounds can therefore find use as broad spectrum pesticide against plant borne fungus and bacteria.

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